

SWOT Analysis as a Basis for Strategies Designed for the Management of Tourism Development in Ukraine

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ABSTRACT

In the current conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, the tourism industry of Ukraine needs more than ever strategic development and the development of a universal scheme of strategic management of tourism development. Prospects for the use of SWOT analysis as an effective management tool will contribute to the implementation in accordance with the selected priorities of regulation and management of tourism development. The study considers the theoretical foundations of using SWOT analysis as one of the tools of strategic analysis. Based on the results of strategic analysis, priorities for tourism development are developed, as well as strategies for counteracting negative factors. Peculiarities and significance of SWOT analysis as a tool for tourism development management in Ukraine in the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic have been studied. In accordance with the selected priorities, modern management concepts for the development of the industry are being implemented. Its main advantages and disadvantages for optimizing the management of tourism and recreation are noted. Factors influencing the development of the tourism industry of Ukraine and Romania based on the use of SWOT analysis are summarized. In the current conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, special attention should be paid to the development of management tools in tourism. One of such effective tools is SWOT analysis, the results of which are the basis for determining the strategic directions of development of the tourism industry and optimizing the management of tourism and recreation.

1. Introduction

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, with the simultaneous escalation of competition, the effective use of the country's comparative advantages in the field of tourism requires additional knowledge and efforts from both state institutions and entrepreneurship. The experience of leading tourism countries shows that an effective tool in conducting effective tourism policy is to use competitive strategies that ensure the active development of tourism in the country, promote a competitive tourism product and help to take a significant place in the international travel services market. One of the methods of diagnosing the development of a tourist-recreation complex at the national level is the study of the internal and external environment using SWOT analysis. This as a method of conducting analytical studies

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of the state of the object is widely used in the practice of strategic planning and has a number of advantages that follow from the algorithm of its implementation. Prospects for the application of SWOT analysis as an effective management tool will promote the implementation, in accordance with selected priorities, regulation and management of tourism development.

2. Literature Review

The general methodology of conducting a SWOT analysis and research on the problems of tourism development management and the introduction of foreign experience of leading tourist countries is reflected in the works of a significant number of scientists and analysts, including: Agrawal (2016), Arulmozhi et al. (2020), Bilgin (2017), Bojović and Plavša (2011), Fernando (2021), Foriş and Foriş (2012), Gülseven (2015), Hlovatska et al. (2013), Islam (2018), Jelev (2016), Josipović et al. (2020), Kantawateera et al. (2013), Kiliçarslan (2019), Lominashvili-Pruidze et al. (2018), Navrozova and Katsyuk (2016), Nicolau et al. (2018), Panova (2020), Plyakov (2020), Shao and Sun (2020), Singh and Kaur (2016), Şerban Comănescu (2017), Tambunan (2020), Tekin and Demirel (2018), Wall (2002).

However, researchers do not fully consider the basis for using SWOT analysis as one of the tools of strategic analysis. Without emphasizing that the results of strategic analysis develop priorities for tourism development, as well as strategies to counteract negative factors. Generalized SWOT analysis of the development of the tourism industry in Ukraine in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and its comparison with EU countries is presented in any of the researches.

3. Methodology

In the event of a global pandemic and the need to overcome its consequences, there is a necessity of identifying the areas that may be favourable for the development of tourism business in Ukraine in the conditions of coronary crisis. The main hypothesis of the article is the study of scientific and practical aspects of the use of SWOT analysis as an important management tool in tourism in Ukraine.

In the process of research we have used a number of general scientific and special methods. Methods of theoretical generalization using elements of analysis (for comprehensive assessment of the state of the tourist sphere of Ukraine and identification of trends in its development; conducting a generalized SWOT analysis of tourism development in Ukraine and Romania); synthesis and comparison (to determine the essence, content, theoretical and practical approaches to conducting SWOT analysis); systematization (to form conclusions). The information base of the research was reported and analytical information of domestic and international organizations; scientific works of domestic and foreign authors, which cover the application of SWOT analysis as a basis for the formation of strategies in the process of managing tourism development, electronic resources presented on the Internet; results of own research.

4. Results and Discussion

Ukraine has a significant tourism potential that could help pull the economy out of the crisis because it is interconnected with many other areas of activity. However, the country's tourism opportunities are not fully realized due to the lack of strategic management of tourism development in Ukraine.

Ukraine recorded a total of 3 million tourists in 2020, ranking 51st in the world in absolute terms (Fig. 1). Without including the size of a country, such a ranking list may not be very meaningful. By putting the tourist numbers in relation to the population of Ukraine, the result is much more comparable picture: With 0.077 tourists per resident, Ukraine ranked 130th in the world. In Eastern Europe, it ranked 8th Ukraine generated around 687.00 million US Dollar in the tourism sector alone. This corresponds to 0.44 percent of its the gross domestic product and approximately 2 percent of all international tourism receipts in Eastern Europe².

Fig. 1. Number of tourists who visited Ukraine in 2020*

Source: Adapted from *Tourism in Ukraine*

*Data in the chart are given in millions of tourists. The red line represents the average of all 10 countries in Eastern Europe.

However, it should be noted that despite all the damage suffered by the tourist sector of Ukraine, there is currently a recovery and gradual growth of tourist collection, as evidenced by statistics for 2021.

In 2021, the community budget received UAH 244 million in tourist fees. This figure is 86.8% higher than in 2020, which amounted to UAH 130.6 million, and 20% higher than in 2019 - then the budget received UAH 196 million. The TOP-5 leaders included the city of Kyiv and 4 regions for the payment of tourist fees. The capital of Ukraine replenished the budget by UAH 68 million, Odesa region earned UAH 26.8 million, third place went to Lvivska - UAH 23 million, fourth - Kyiv with UAH 15.3 million. In fifth place - the Transcarpathian region, which earned UAH 11.7 million, which is twice as much as in 2020, when budget revenue was UAH 5.6 million (1news.com.ua, 2022).

It can be convincingly stated that tourism in Ukraine has a high potential for development in such products, as weekend tours and business tourism (MICE) as

² <https://www.worlddata.info/europe/ukraine/tourism.php>

well as in the field of natural and cultural resources (for example, rural tourism, medical institutions / health centers). However, due to the lack of effective strategic management of the industry and non-competitiveness in the international market, its development is significantly hampered.

Nowadays Ukrainian tourism has not received a rapid systemic response from the government in the form of the introduction of possible measures to support the tourism industry, compared with the average response and types of measures implemented by governments of neighboring countries and EU members. This further complicates the situation of small and medium-sized businesses working in the fields of hospitality, tourism and recreation.

Experts from Euler Hermes, a world leader in credit insurance and receivables management, believe that the situation in the international tourism industry is normalized no earlier than two years (Livinec & Adjiman, 2021). This assessment is confirmed by the results of a recent survey of industry representatives conducted by the United Nations World Tourism Organization. Most respondents noted that, in their opinion, international tourism will return to the level reached before the COVID-19 pandemic, at best in 2023. Forty-one percent of respondents believe that normalization will take place only in 2024 or even later (Table 1).

Table 1. Tourist flow in the world in 2017–2024, million people

Millions	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022f	2023f	2024f
World	1333	1408	1459	400	550	800	1200	1400
Europe	677	716	744	227	281	406	655	771
APAC	323	347	361	64	119	178	267	326
North America	137	142	146	47	71	94	112	136
Africa	63	68	70	22	27	38	51	63
Middle East	58	60	65	17	24	37	49	58

Source: Adapted from Livinec and Adjiman (2021)

An analysis by Euler Hermes experts showed that Europe, compared to other regions, will lead the recovery of the tourism industry, although the economy as a whole will recover faster in the United States and the Asia-Pacific region. According to the forecast Euler Hermes, already in 2024 Europe can be visited by 771 million foreign tourists. For comparison, in 2020. there were only 227 million, or more than three times less. In Europe, the number of tourists arriving will grow at an advanced pace compared to other regions of the world, as in 2020. it is this region that has experienced the biggest decline in this regard (in absolute numbers, the number of foreign tourists who visited Europe in 2020), decreased by more than 500 million people compared to 2019). In addition, Euler Hermes experts expect EU countries to work together to remove travel restrictions in the most optimal way: Europe will benefit the most from the resurgence of tourism (Livinec & Adjiman, 2021).

The current level of severity of quarantine restrictions worldwide is reflected in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Index of severity of quarantine restrictions during 2020
Source: Adapted from Livinec and Adjiman (2021)

Europe remains a leader against the backdrop of other parts of the world - almost 10 points compared to North America and 20 points compared to the Asia-Pacific region. The current level of tourism depends to a large extent on this index, and this explains why tourism in the European region has suffered the most. Only domestic tourism will be able to return to normal pre-pandemic pace of development until 2022. However, the revival of domestic tourism does not compensate for the losses for the industry as a whole, incurred due to the reduction in the number of more profitable international and business trips. These market segments may have a negative impact until 2023. Tourists traveling within their countries usually spend less money than international tourists. It is expected that the volume of tourists' expenses for international travel even in 2023, will be 8% less pre-crisis (Livinec & Adjiman, 2021). Rising unemployment will also exacerbate problems for the tourism industry, as people are likely to cut travel costs.

Today, Ukraine lags far behind in shaping the country's tourism development strategy, which poses a serious threat to the industry's competitiveness in the global market during the projected recovery in 2021-2022. Currently, only UAH 4 billion is allocated to interest compensation on existing loans for micro and small enterprises, a somewhat expanded program of available loans (5-7-9%); UAH 24 billion - to provide loans with state investment guarantees; UAH 1.6 billion - to support the tourism industry. Temporary material unemployment benefits are also provided for those, who lost his job as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, paid in the amount of two-thirds of the amount of wages for each reduced working hour, but not more

than the fixed amount, namely: the established minimum monthly salary (currently only UAH 6,500, or €195) increase in pensions and unemployment benefits (Bagrii, 2021).

We believe that the most important stage in the formation of the strategy for tourism development in Ukraine is strategic and competitive analysis. One of the important tools of strategic analysis is SWOT analysis, which is widely used in foreign practice of corporate governance. This universal method is especially effective in analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of the country's tourism market. Based on the results of strategic analysis, tourism development priorities are developed, as well as strategies to counter negative factors. SWOT analysis helps to clarify the circumstances in which Ukraine's tourism market is developing, to balance the impact of internal advantages and disadvantages with the impact of favorable opportunities and threats. Such an analysis helps to identify not only the country's capabilities, but also all available benefits over competitors.

The SWOT analysis process identifies threats and opportunities that may arise in the external environment, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of the study object. Having done SWOT analysis, it will be possible to identify the main strategy for tourism development in the region and specific areas to stimulate the development of this industry, as the most dynamic, highly profitable, environmentally friendly, low-energy. Based on the SWOT analysis, it is possible to explain the strategic interpretation of the impact of the described factors on the trends of entry, exit and domestic tourism.

There are many definitions of SWOT analysis, but they all come down to assessing strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats (Agrawal, 2016; Arulmozhi et al., 2020; Bilgin, 2017; Bojović & Plavša, 2011; Fernando, 2021; Foriş & Foriş, 2012; Gülseven, 2015; Hlovatska et al., 2013; Islam, 2018; Jelev, 2016; Josipović et al., 2020; Kantawateera et al., 2013; Lominashvili-Pruidze et al., 2018; Navrozova & Katsyuk, 2016; Nicolau et al., 2018; Panova, 2020; Plyakov, 2020; Shao & Sun, 2020; Shi et al., 2014; Singh & Kaur, 2016; Şerban Comănescu, 2017; Tambunan, 2020; Tekin & Demirel, 2018; Wall, 2002). In today's conditions under SWOT analysis, as an important management tool in tourism, should be understood: analysis, which allows to generalize the strengths and weaknesses of the tourism industry, destinies (internal environment) opportunities and threats from other industries (external environment) the results of which are the basis for management decisions on the strategic development of the tourism industry.

The most important stage of SWOT analysis, in our opinion, is the awareness of threats. Threats are external factors that are a barrier, an obstacle, a danger, or incur additional costs (Shelenko & Smushak, 2012). As threats exist and are difficult to influence, measures must be taken to avoid negative consequences. Ignoring threats can lead to the loss of markets, inhibiting tourism development, and this, in turn, to a slowdown in economic development in general. Realizing the obstacles that can shake the created tourism infrastructure, carefully assessing the problems that will arise in the way of development of the industry, we will be able to form

measures to avoid them or reduce their action on the development of the tourism industry. The next step will be to build a hierarchy of opportunities that the industry can use to achieve positive results through the implementation of strategic goals.

These are new opportunities that will be necessary and useful in the future for the constant updating of travel services and progress. In general, opportunities are trends and changes in the business environment that can be used to stimulate development and overcome existing difficulties (Shelenko & Smushak, 2012).

Taking into account all four components of SWOT analysis in the complex will allow to identify the main strategic directions of tourism development, to formulate goals and specific tasks. In addition, SWOT analysis will allow to outline a plan for strategic development of the tourism industry in the future, to forecast the necessary actions and means, to take into account new opportunities.

The following is a summary of the SWOT analysis of tourism development in Ukraine and Romania, on the basis of which it is possible to compare the individual directions, shortcomings and advantages of tourism activities (Tables 2, 3).

Table 2. SWOT analysis of the tourism industry of Ukraine

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ancient unique historical and cultural heritage; ▪ High level of education of the population; ▪ Favorable geographical location of Ukraine; ▪ High transport potential; ▪ Seven wonders of Ukraine that can be compared to the world; ▪ Friendly population; ▪ Opportunities for the development of all types of tourism; ▪ Increasing competition from tour operators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Low quality of tourist services; ▪ Outdated tourist infrastructure that does not meet European quality standards; ▪ Unsatisfactory state of transport infrastructure of the country, low quality of transportation services; ▪ Public funding of tourism; ▪ Lack of a formed holistic brand of Ukraine and imperfection of the regulatory framework; ▪ Lack of a national information system in the field of tourism and resorts and its integration into the world information tourism network.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of domestic tourism; ▪ Promotion of the country in other regions and continents; ▪ Improving the environmental situation; ▪ Improving public policy; ▪ Introduction of a competitive-capable national tourism product; ▪ Introduction of economic and legal mechanisms for successful tourism business; ▪ Investment mechanisms for the development of tourist infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unstable political situation (events related to the annexation of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the conduct of military action with the Russian Federation in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions - until 24.02.2022). Beginning on February 24, 2022, a full-scale war with the Russian Federation to preserve the independence and integrity of Ukraine; ▪ Technogenic catastrophes - wear and tear of infrastructure and communications; ▪ Increasing the price of travel services, reducing demand; ▪ Financial and economic crisis; ▪ The possibility of epidemiological diseases and the demographic crisis; ▪ Tourism development in close EU countries.

Source: Author's elaboration

Primary data: <https://www.worlddata.info/europe/ukraine/tourism.php>

Table 3. SWOT analysis of the Romanian tourism industry

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The presence on the Romanian tourism market of world-famous hotel chains (Mariott, Hilton, HolidayInn, Best Western) guaranteeing the quality of services offered to tourists; ▪ Favourable geographic location at the intersection of the large Euro-Asian transport routes, opening to the Black Sea; ▪ Possession of patents and / or technologies that give the tourism enterprises a competitive character; ▪ The existence of tourist culture and the possibility of developing all forms of tourism due to the diversity of the harmoniously distributed tourist potential; ▪ Increasing tourist loyalty towards some of the products / services offered; ▪ National Tourism Development Program (“Skiing in the Carpathians”, “Ski area Predeal-Azuga”, “Wine Road”) and social programs (“Country holidays”, “The seaside for all”) initiated by the national tourism authority. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The quality level and the low degree of diversification of tourist services (emphasis is placed on accommodation and food); ▪ The shady increase in the number of accommodation places in the tourist reception facilities; ▪ Lack of cooperation between economic operators operating in tourism; ▪ The constantly low average index of use of the accommodation capacity, around 34.5%; ▪ Insufficient tourist information and promotion (especially on the Internet); ▪ Insufficiently developed and non-modernized tourism base (the large share of old accommodation structures); ▪ The existence of an inadequate infrastructure, physically or morally worn off; ▪ Shortcomings in the training of the workforce specialized in tourism; ▪ Inappropriate cost strategies compared to the quality of the products offered; ▪ Poorly developed telecommunication networks; ▪ Unfriendly business environment for foreign investors; ▪ Reduced contribution of the tourism sector to GDP formation (below 3%); ▪ Significant deviations of the competitiveness and quality of tourism services, the consequences of this policy being manifested today by changing tourists’ preferences to tourist destinations outside the borders; ▪ Very low investments in tourism of the total investments in the economy below 2%; ▪ Lack of an effective marketing policy; ▪ The instability of the governmental institutional framework with a role and attributions in the elaboration of the tourism policy and strategy; ▪ The seasonal character of the mountain and seaside tourist market; ▪ Poverty of the population; ▪ Lack of a good management policy at all levels; ▪ Competition of resorts in Bulgaria, Turkey, Greece.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognition on the domestic and international tourism market as a result of Romania’s accession to the European Union; thus, it is estimated that the number of foreign EU tourists visiting Romania will increase but not spectacularly; this increase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Entering the competition as a holiday destination with the new member states of the European Union; thus the quality of the products / services offered will become a decisive factor in the choice of a destination or operator by the tourist;

<p>rather joins the general trend in the European tourism industry;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Providing tax incentives for new investments, depending on the size of investment in tourism enterprises; ▪ Tourism development by attracting structural funds from the European Union, allowing the support and financing of projects in this field; ▪ Ongoing projects - support for future tourist activity: highways, rail transport modernization, sea transport terminal for tourists, etc.; ▪ Freedom of movement of persons, services, goods, capital; ▪ Diversification of tourists' pricing according to comfort and season in order to promote tourism for young people, for low-income tourists, for schoolchildren; ▪ The single Euro currency, which has brought and will bring great benefits to tourism by simplicity (the tourist will have with him/her a single currency), transparency (the tourist will be familiar with the purchasing power of the currency), saving time and commissions; ▪ Interactive museums; interactive craft workshops; small industrial workshops that work on the tourist's command: glassware, ceramics, metal engraving, goblets; ▪ Elaboration and implementation of tourism development strategy by NTA; (several priorities of the strategy: creating and promoting the national tourist brand, developing a national network of Tourist Information and Promotion Centres); ▪ Tourist attractions by diversifying tourism with packages up to personalization and taking into account the entire national potential; ▪ Attracting investors, especially foreign, with management input. Concession of land on advantageous conditions to investors, including for the setting up of new resorts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Migration of the highly skilled labour force and tourism to the European Union, especially due to the very low salaries paid in Romania, compared to the external offer; ▪ Unattractive environment for foreign investors due to the fiscal policy of the state; ▪ Migration of Romanian tourists. Exit from European tourism flows; ▪ Degradation of the natural environment through different types of pollution; ▪ Increasing competition pressure; ▪ Vulnerability to business environment fluctuations; ▪ Deepening of the effects of the economic and financial crisis at national and international level; ▪ Changes in the preferences, needs, tastes of tourists; ▪ Expansion of viruses, which have had and still have devastating effects; ▪ Entering of new competitors on the tourist market; ▪ Enterprises that are located in low-attractiveness resorts will experience lower performance and will have to pursue an aggressive investment policy; terrorist acts, regional wars and other types of crisis Situations; ▪ Labour productivity within the tourism activity is strongly influenced by factors such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › the tourist attractiveness of the tourist area; › the size and intensity of tourist flows; › climatic conditions; › conjunctural factors.
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Source: Adapted from Șerban Comănescu (2017)

Let's make a pair of comparisons of all strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats to the tourist market of Ukraine in Table. 4.

Table 4. Pairwise comparison of SWOT analysis criteria

		Opportunities							Threats						Сума
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Strengths	1	5	3	0	4	5	1	5	-1	0	0	0	0	1	23
	2	4	3	0	4	5	0	5	-3	1	-2	0	0	1	18
	3	5	3	1	5	5	0	5	-1	-3	0	0	0	1	21
	4	5	1	0	0	5	0	5	-1	0	0	0	0	1	16
	5	5	0	0	0	5	0	2	-1	-1	0	1	0	1	12
	6	0	5	0	0	0	5	3	-1	0	-3	0	0	2	11
	7	0	4	5	5	5	1	4	-3	-4	0	3	0	0	20
	8	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	-1	0	0	-1	0	1	2
Weaknesses	1	-5	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	-5	0	0	0	-1	-4	-17
	2	0	-2	0	-2	-1	-5	0	-5	0	0	0	-3	-4	-22
	3	0	-3	0	-1	-1	-2	-3	-5	-1	0	0	-5	-5	-26
	4	-1	-5	-3	-1	-3	0	-1	-5	-1	-5	-4	-4	-5	-38
	5	0	0	0	0	-1	-5	0	-5	-2	-3	-2	0	-5	-23
	6	0	0	0	0	0	-4	0	-5	0	0	-5	-1	0	-15
Сума	18	9	3	13	26	-9	25	-42	-11	-13	-8	-14	-15		

Source: Author's calculations

Primary data: <https://www.worlddata.info/europe/ukraine/tourism.php>

The results of Table 4 show that the strongest parties are the long-standing unique historical and cultural heritage, the favorable geographical location of Ukraine and with a slight lag - opportunities for the development of all types of tourism. The weakest side is the state financing of tourism, in second place - the lack of a formed integral brand of Ukraine and the imperfection of the regulatory framework, and in third place, with a lag of 2 points from second place - unsatisfactory state of transport infrastructure, low quality of transportation services.

Among the main opportunities can be distinguished the introduction of a competitive national tourism product; investment mechanisms for the development of tourist infrastructure - in second place, the development of domestic tourism - in third place. The biggest threat was the events related to the annexation of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the conduct of military action with the Russian Federation in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions - until February 24, 2022. Currently, the threat that has led to a complete halt to the Ukrainian tourism industry, beginning on February 24, 2022, is a full-scale war with the Russian Federation to preserve Ukraine's independence and integrity. Also, a pairwise comparison of the criteria of SWOT analysis showed that the main threats to the tourist market of Ukraine are the significant development of tourism in close EU countries, which are direct competitors for the domestic market of tourism services. Also significant threats are the demographic crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic, which has hit the country's tourism services market very badly.

Thus, in order for the tourism business in Ukraine to develop, it is first necessary to complete hostilities and ensure the complete security of the country from threats from the Russian Federation, thus leveling the demographic threat of

moving the flow of citizens abroad. According to the UN as of March 8, 2022. since the beginning of Russian aggression, Ukraine has left 1.7 million citizens. Of these, only 50-70 thousand crossed the border of Russia/Belarus, while the vast majority went to Poland (50%+), Hungary (12%), Moldova (8%), Slovakia (8%) and Romania (5%).) (Fig. 3). In the long run it is necessary to establish a stable service and create a holistic brand of the country through the development of new thematic tours based on historical, geographical and landscape riches of Ukraine (UNHCR, 2022).

Fig. 3. Number of refugees from Ukraine to neighboring countries as of March 8, 2022
 Source: Adapted from UNHCR (2022)

Characterizing the tourist market of neighboring Romania, it should be emphasized that it is a famous center of international tourism. Romania's leading tourist centers are the attractions of Bucharest, Braşov, Iaşi, Oradea, Timişoara, Sighişoara, Constanţa, Alba-Iulia, Cluj-Napoca, Suceava and others. Transylvania, where many cultural sites are concentrated is attractive for tourists. The business card of Transylvania is Bran Castle (Dracula's Castle), a literary vampire - Count Dracula - the hero of Bram Stoker's novel *Dracula* and the mountain massif of Transfăgărăşan. Interesting for tourists are the medieval cities of Braşov, Sibiu, Sighişoara, Alba-Iulia, Cluj-Napoca, Sfîntu Gheorghe, Tîrgu Mureş, Oradea, Bistriţa, as well as many Saxon settlements with unique fortified churches such as Prejmer or Hărman.

Historically connected with European culture, Romania is a kind and exotic country. Recently, tourism in Romania is developing at a fairly rapid pace, and this industry has become an important component of the Romanian economy. Romania is recorded in total of 5 million tourists in 2020, ranking 37th in the world in absolute terms. Romania generated around 1.61 billion US Dollar in the tourism sector alone. This corresponds to 0.65 percent of its the gross domestic product and approximately

6 percent of all international tourism receipts in Eastern Europe³. The number of tourists staying in Romania jumped by 46.4% on the year to 9,376 million in 2021. Tourists spent 20.65 million in Romania in 2021, up 43% year-on-year. Foreign tourist numbers surged by annual 83.6% to 1.82 million during January-December. In December 2021 alone, total tourist numbers rose by an annual 69.5%, as the number of foreign tourist was 141% higher on the year (Bănilă, 2022).

The reasons for the growth of tourism in Romania are very clear. Romania is a very diverse country. Here everyone can find classes and spend their time to their preferences. A significant number of Romanian travel companies are ready to meet tourists and offer guests of Romania a variety of tours: ski resorts in the Carpathians in winter and holidays on the beaches of the Black Sea in summer, excursions to fortresses and castles of Romania and ancient Romanian cities, eco-tourism and more. It should be noted that vacationing in Romania is much cheaper than in other countries of the European Union, and in some cities cheaper than in Ukraine.

The SWOT analysis (Table 3) reflects a “delicate” situation in which Romania find itself currently. There are also many of the works faced by tourism, but also a number of importunities related primarily to Romania’s recent integration into the European Union. The analysis can be used to detect strengths, correct and diminish weaknesses, eliminate threats and capitalize on exportunities through strategic planning. Therefore, we sugar investment in infrastructure and in the promotional activities of cultural tourism, ecotourism, business tourism and in the world stop here, beautiful Romania has an infinity.

SWOT analysis of tourism development in Ukraine and Romania indicates internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats (risks) that will affect the development of the tourism industry. The strength of their interaction and their combination determine the competitiveness of turproduct of these countries in foreign markets.

We believe that in terms of strategic management, SWOT analysis has many advantages:

- is an early stage of strategic planning for most tourist firms;
- is an integral part of the process of developing the strategy of the travel company;
- is an information basis for the formation of strategic problems and alternative strategic solutions;
- involves joint study of external and internal environments;
- involves the establishment of paired combinations between threats, opportunities in the external environment, on the one hand, and the strengths and weaknesses of the organization, on the other;
- focuses on the factors that affect the competitive position and competitive advantages of the organization;

³ <https://www.worlddata.info/europe/romania/tourism.php>

- provides the following sequence of research of environmental factors: tracking changes in the factor → analysis of the state of the factor → identification of the nature of the impact of the factor on the firm → forecasting the possible effects of the impact of the factor on the firm in the future;
- widely uses expert assessments;
- provides a mandatory score assessment of the factors of the macro-environment, the immediate environment and the internal environment of the organization.

The benefits of SWOT analysis are a comprehensive assessment of opportunities and risks, strengths and weaknesses; deepening the understanding of business, managers and professionals; rapid transition from the analysis process to strategic planning. Regarding the shortcomings of SWOT analysis - this is subjectivism: the inability to take into account all strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats; subjectivity of choice and ranking of factors of the external and internal environment; poor adaptation to an ever-changing environment.

In the context of European integration processes in tourism, the application of SWOT analysis should be combined with other management tools that improve the quality of the travel product to international standards, attract more consumers of travel services, which, according to researchers, are not satisfied with the assessment of cost-quality parameters. Thus, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, special attention should be paid to the development of management tools in tourism.

5. Conclusion

The research shows that the development of tourism in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic remains outside the key interests of the state and business in Ukraine, unlike neighboring Romania. The key priorities for the sustainable development of the travel and tourism industry, the stable growth of its global competitiveness are the issues of epidemiological protection and simplification of regulation in this sector, conservation of cultural and natural resources, increasing their attractiveness to foreign tourists, and ensuring high priority of the sector in public policy.

The existing tourist potential of Ukraine can be realized through the introduction of effective approaches and for the development of tourism and recreation and property management of tourist and resort complexes. Based on the SWOT analysis of strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats to the development of the tourism industry in Ukraine, it can be concluded that the promising development of tourism in the country should be based on the following components: normalization of political, economic and legislative climate; investment and innovation in infrastructure development; reorganization of transport support; training of qualified personnel, etc.

The study showed that the results of SWOT analysis are the basis for the formation and definition of strategic directions for the development of the tourism industry and optimization of tourism and recreation management in Ukraine.

Prospects for further exploration in this direction are the construction of multi-vector strategies for the development of the tourism industry of Ukraine in the postwar period using the means and properties of SWOT analysis.

Unfortunately, there is a full-scale war with the Russian Federation today to preserve Ukraine's independence and integrity, which makes it impossible to develop tourism in the near future. But Ukraine is a strong state with an unbreakable and invincible nation that has chosen European values to protect them with its life. Glory to Ukraine! Glory to heroes!

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